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Habit-Induced Concept of Human Motivation and Strategic Peace Building Approach in the World

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Author: Ashraf ud Dowla & Nurul Hasan

Abstract: Throughout history, philosophers, scholars, and social scientists have attempted to comprehend the true nature of the inner force that drives every human action and attitude. People endeavored to know 'thymself' to realize the sources of their own feelings, emotions, strengths, potentials, senses of interest, and causes of human conflicts. Enormous study findings are also available to identify the core source of human motivation that drives unity or disputes among people. Conflict reduction is one of the core agendas in peace-building, where strategic peace-building demands a long-term sustainable approach to eradicate causes of conflicts among people and nations. In a meta-analysis of human behavior, attitude, and actions related to peace and conflict, this study focus on the core nature of human behavior through a neurobiological evolutionary lens. A habit-induced model of human behavior can explain the needs of every human feelings, behaviors, and actions from birth to the termination of each life and possess a profound link in intra and international peace-building. The study finds a more robust strategic peace-building technique for humanity through an in-depth comprehension of the human mind.

Keywords: *Habit, Behavior, conflict, Peace-building*

Habit-Induced Concept of Human Motivation and Strategic Peace Building Approach in the World

Ashraf -ud-Dowla

The author has a keen interest on human-centric security and the scientific approach to human motivation. He believes soft skills are:

- The primary determinants of quality in life.
- The driving force of societies.
- The root of leadership success.

Although his academic life started as a student at the Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology, the beauty of the virtuous institution attracted him to join the military. Apart from military training and courses at home, he received a credential among the top 5% university graduates from the Logistical Engineering University, Chongqing, China. He pursued his 2nd Master's in Peace and Conflict Management. As a Ph.D. (fellow) at the Bangladesh University of Professionals, he is now working to explore the impact of new media on shaping the dreams and aspirations of future citizens in Bangladesh

Nurul Hasan

On the journey to be a professional psychologist, the author has completed his BSc(Hons) and Masters in Psychology. He is keenly interested in Social Psychology, Abnormal Psychology, Counselling, and Psychometrics. He is a research fellow at the Bangladesh University of Professionals (BUP). In his professional life, he has also participated in a number of national and International education courses and seminars on human behavioral issues. As a student of leadership and human motivation, his research area includes exploring the impact of transformational leadership on job satisfaction in different types of organizational climates.

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Abstract

Throughout history, philosophers, scholars, and social scientists have attempted to comprehend the true nature of the inner force that drives every human action and attitude. People endeavored to know 'thyself' to realize the sources of their own feelings, emotions, strengths, potentials, senses of interest, and causes of human conflicts. Enormous study findings are also available to identify the core source of human motivation that drives unity or disputes among people. Conflict reduction is one of the core agendas in peace-building, where strategic peace-building demands a long-term sustainable approach to eradicate causes of conflicts among people and nations. In a meta-analysis of human behavior, attitude, and actions related to peace and conflict, this study focus on the core nature of human behavior through a neurobiological evolutionary lens. A habit-induced model of human behavior can explain the needs of every human feelings, behaviors, and actions from birth to the termination of each life and possess a profound link in intra and international peace-building. The study finds a more robust strategic peace-building technique for humanity through an in-depth comprehension of the human mind.

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Introduction

Shape, size, colour, and physical structure differ among species, but behaviour and mental capacity differentiate humans and their identity. How a person interacts with others, responds to situations, and displays behaviours that speak about his identity. Habit of constructive behaviour allows people to win the crown of success, and destructive one puts people to go ashtray. The development comes from constructive human habits, and conflicts originate from diverse mental conditionings. A sense of the need for survival, propagation of own species, and the power of habit essentially control every feeling of human needs and their actions.

According to psychological study, human actions or the behaviour demands an in-depth understanding of two broad spectrum: unlearned and learned behaviour. Unlearned behaviours are displayed naturally with time as human babies grow from infancy to adulthood. The unlearned behaviours pass through generations as an inheritance. A newborn infant displays some behaviour like: crying to express distress, facial expressions for unhappiness, and moving hands and legs upon joy; these are a few unlearned behaviours. In comparison to other living creatures, humans inherit only a few such identical capacities when they are born but they learn most behaviors from the society to realize survival, growth, and reproduction. The superior

human brain and the grand design of human life take every opportunity to learn new skills and build habits for higher survival, individual growth, and social needs.

Understanding Innate Human Needs

In pursuing the core stimulation of human behaviour, scientists have made a variety of conclusions. The ancient Greek philosopher Plato coined, “Human behaviour flows from three primary sources: desire, emotion, and knowledge.” Abraham Maslow explained five core needs that form the basis for every behavioral motivation: physiological needs, safety needs, love-belongingness needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization needs (Maslow, 1942). Clayton Alderfer’s concluded human necessities that shape every human motivation and action are growth needs, existing needs, and relatedness (Alderfer, 1969). David McClelland identified three motivators that all humans possess: a need for achievement, a need for affiliation, and a need for power (McClelland, 1961). British Psychologist Albert Bandura explained that most human behaviour is learned observationally through modelling from others (Bandura, 1977). These existing theories to describe human wills, behavior, and learning possess some unique strengths and insights yet have limitations. However, almost all theories of human motivation and actions possess a common element that human behaviour results from specific biological or psychological needs. It says that behaviours either learned or unlearned are the outcome of the needs of life.

Major Theories	Limitations
Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human needs are often overlaps and do not follow sequences • Humans are often found pursuing higher needs even without meeting the lower level as described in the theory • It does not explain the behaviors of insane humans
ERG Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It also does not explain the behaviors of insane humans • The ERG theory does not describe needs of addicted humans who are habituated in certain destructive behavior
Reinforcement Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It does not explain the human needs originate through the internal biological predispositions. • It also does not speak about the behaviors of insane humans.
David McClelland Theory of Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It also does not explain the behaviors of insane humans. • The theory does not describe needs of addicted humans who are habituated in certain destructive behavior. • It does not explain the human needs originate through the internal biological predispositions and the needs of reproductive impulses.

Figure 1: Authors Illustration on Major Theories of Human Motivation

Behaviour spontaneously shapes or manifests between the cause and effect, where *needs* are the causes and behaviours are the effects. Necessities make humans act and respond to whatever is

perceived by the brain as the best to act. The word 'perceive' encompasses the conscious understanding and unconscious evaluation of situations by the central nervous system that evaluates and decides whatever necessary for our well-being. As we experience something new, we essentially realize it depending upon our previous knowledge, wisdom, habit, and inborn unlearned mental skills. Unlearned behaviour generally transmits from generation to generation; however, the specific learned behaviour may also genetically transmit to the offspring as an evolutionary design of our life.

As most theories have underscored, 'need' is the trigger of human behaviour; therefore, the term 'need' demands a deep understanding of what it means. In the theories of human motivation, *need* is explained as a conscious or unconscious sense of necessities as perceived by the automatic nervous system of the brain. It encompasses every understanding, feeling, and stimulation the human brain generates to move on to life journey. These feelings are primarily beyond someone's conscious comprehension. As conscious living beings, we experience different emotions and feelings each day and each moment. We feel hungry and eat food; we feel thirsty and thus drink water. We feel happy to see the beautiful ocean beach and enjoy time with friends and families. We experience thousands of such emotions, likings, and dislikes but often remain ignorant about the core source of such feelings. Indeed, the brain is the command centre that constantly receives stimulations, evaluates, generates directions, beyond our ordinary consciousness as it perceives necessary. *Needs* are the results of our feelings originate from the most sophisticated neuroscientific functions of our brain.

A Habit-Induced Concept of Human Motivation

Human needs and motivation may be understood more comprehensively through a meta-analysis of the human mind. The neurobiological study explains a profound explanation of human behaviour, which can probably elucidate every bit of peoples' response from all gender and age with diverse cognitive functions, irrespective of time, context, and group identity. Studies of the human brain through the most advanced technologies have found that every human behaviour, sense, and feeling is the outcome of brain functions and an interplay of different neurotransmitters. It says electrically excitable cells of around 86 billion neurons and another 85 billion glial cells densely compacted in a tiny space of our skull build commands for our every sense and actions. Trillions of highly sophisticated complex synaptic connections among brain neurons constitute a giant network inside the human brain that profoundly direct each human response to situations and observed behavior.

Scientists have discovered that a significant level of connections among brain neurons exists when a human baby is born, thus we observe some unlearned or inherent actions, responses, and

behaviour among infants. These inherent default neuronal networks function for immediate survival needs and invest in both learning for short-term and long-term necessities in life. However, most parts of the brain neurons connect and form networks as human learn from experiences, observation, and through the induction stimuli of the environment. Humans are born most vulnerable as such the acute necessity of survival through learning enriches the human capacity to innovate and develop. Humans learn what all are essential for life individually and collectively. As our every feelings and senses are the result of neuronal networks functioning inside the brain, our life needs are also the outcome of those ultra microscopic connections and stimuli that transform into a feeling of motivation. It exhibits as the output of the brain impulses and networking of neurons that trigger human behaviour through a sense of need either consciously or beyond awareness.

Human biological functions run independently by the central nervous system beyond someones' choices. However, the grand design of being social creatures, humans possess an acute necessity to learn new skills and behaviours. Due to the need for massive cooperation, our brain seeks every opportunity to master new skills to create more affiliation with others. Our central nervous system takes every decision to realize growth and development as part of the higher survival needs in society. The ultra-smart human brain constantly and continuously remains engaged to observe, listen, visualize, experience, and learn to attain the superior survival and reproduction needs. Higher survival needs in humans motivate and create more innovative ideas to grow, construct, create, and develop. Indeed, modern human civilization is the outcome of the sense of higher survival needs.

Education, knowledge, wisdom, and habit play a significant role in defining survival needs in human life. People dedicate themselves to pursuing money, status, name, fame, and power for perceived higher survival needs. Conversely, people with higher wisdom feels motivated to survive and progress through the power of unity and cooperation to materialize even higher survival. Due to limited vision and knowledge, some people may contest for societal power and individual growth to fulfil immediate or short-term needs but visionary humans engage themselves to eradicate status differences among people for an even greater long-term unity and development needs.

Survival *needs* and reproduction *needs* are the two core *needs* in human life, but those *needs* materialize through diverse learning processes. Learning new and newer skills improves human survival and define progress. The legacy of learning habits shape society and civilization. In the way of attaining higher degree of survival, learning becomes a need; however, learning occurs through habit-building techniques. Our brain uses the sophisticated system while learning new skills in the most energy-efficient way. In habit-building, our brain creates a neuronal path combined with a dopamine reward system. As such, when we learn something new, it transforms

into our habits, and when a routine develops, we instinctively feel happy to follow our patterns. Thus the reward system generates a sense of happiness to comply with the command of our habits; and we repeat and further repeat the same behaviour.

When a habit gets a shape, the pattern itself becomes a source of need in our life due to the dopamine effect of the reward system. The reward system thus continuously encourages us and creates an inner force to follow our habits. When we practice constructive habits, we find ourselves skilled and proficient in our behaviour. When we follow our physical habits, we develop physical skills, and when we engage in building our mental habits, we find our identity. Physical habits may have a terminal point, but mental habits are often endless. Proficiency in running or swimming may have an end but the habit of money-making, pursuing power, and status have essentially no limit. We lead our life a little by our knowledge, education or belief but a lot by the habits. When a habit builds, it starts controlling our life more than any other needs and even sometimes supersedes our survival and reproduction needs.

Therefore, we may theorize, "**Human behaviors are defined by three interconnected mutually inclusive needs – survival needs, reproduction needs, and habit needs.**"

Figure 2: Authors Illustration of Habit Induced Motivation Concept

In the Need of Habits

"Father of American psychology William James wrote:

" All our life, so far as it has definite form, is but a mass of habits - practical, emotional, and intellectual - systematically organized for our weal or woe, and bearing us irresistibly toward our destiny, whatever the latter may be."

All humans possess an inborn genetic need to survive and propagate their species as all other living beings on earth. Such an urge motivates humans to display interconnected behaviours and actions in diverse forms. In childhood, survival needs become the priority; as such, most instincts

of life engage in building a healthy physical body, yet reproduction instincts mostly dominate over other feelings during adulthood. Although the human brain constantly generates impulses for higher survival and reproduction, that function continues through building supportive habits by the brain to conserve energy. Habits are the finest output of our grand design of energy-efficient human brain. The human brain is only 2% of the body mass and consumes around 50% to 60% of body energy during infancy and childhood. Infants and children spend most time for learning new skills that means their brain neurons engage in huge activities to build new networks through durable synaptic connections. Such brain activities consumes vast energy, but the human brain - the most intelligent device, seeks for every scope to conserve power. It applies the habit-building scheme and reduces energy consumption to around 20%. An innate yet unconscious biological necessity to conserve power helps us build habits.

We experience our life is a mass of habits, and we build our life through our constructive habits. Habits are physical and mental; habits may be learned and unlearned. Although humans inherit a basket of habits as unlearned behaviour, most of our living habits are shaped in our early life through repetitive experiences and responses as part of learning in daily life. People build habits when they learn and practice regularly and repeatedly. Our brain always functions to build essential new habits and also engage in protecting the old one. Although, survival and reproduction are the most innate needs in life, habit takes control of our behavior even sometimes superseding the previous two. Habit takes almost full command of our behaviour in life in the form of physical activities or mental outputs.

Habit Shapes Human Life

Warren Buffett said, “Chains of habit are too light to be felt until they are too heavy to be broken.” Aristotle pointed out that quality of work is not an act; it is a habit. The Greek philosopher Plutarch explained that human character is a habit long continued. Indeed, our life identity and success are defined and determined by the mass of our constructive or destructive habits. Due to intuitive motivation in response to the necessity of survival and reproduction, human learn new skills and accumulate life habits. We form our habits on what is practised and preached in our surroundings. As a natural tendency to conform with group identity and power, we start to believe what others believe and like what others do. We also sense to dislike, disagree, and disbelieve in similar ways.

Our life is time bounded; we are habit-bounded entities as well. During childhood we learn and build our essential habits however, in adulthood, our daily lives roll on primarily through habits. The degree and quality of our constructive habits help us to work faster, move faster, and accomplish tasks faster with accuracy. The quality of our physical habits determine our skill and proficiency in our work. Conversely, our psychological or mental habits define, how we think, evaluate situations, comment on specific issues, perceive values, believe, and sense interest in

life. Our individual mental habits build individual human characters but collective psychological habits speak about our social identity. Although physical and mental habits are much intertwined and often challenging to study independently, physical habits determine our technical ability, and mental habits tell us about what we are.

Mental Habits Define Our Identity

Humans are predominantly defined by their mental capacity. Knowledge, education, wisdom, passion, and a sense of beauty and justice are our mental habits that develop over time. Our mental habits of willpower, sense of belongingness, group identity, pride, dignity, and honour originate as we learn from our society. Physical habits define our physical skills but the mental habits control our decisions. Humans inherit certain mental habits as inborn cognitive abilities; however, we attain most of our cognitive, social and emotional skills by building mental habits from our surroundings.

The perception of beauty and ugly, rationality and judgment, melodious or cacophonous, is the outcome of our mental capacity. Skills like swimming, riding, driving, and marching are our physical capacity; however, senses and feeling like perception, patriotism, group identity, nationality, foresightedness, vision, and leadership skills are keenly related to our mental habits. The opinion of good or bad generates through our mental pattern. The sense of beauty differs from society, time, and context, which are also essentially the outcome of our mental habits. People unite by the identical psychological habits but they engage in conflict due to the diverse mental conditionings. When people engage in logical thinking, eventually, logical thinking becomes a passion, and people unearth scientific discoveries. Motivation in scientists, leaders, artists, and patriots is the outcome of their passion – a mental habit of loving their work.

Path to Build Constructive Mental Habits

The norms, cultures, and belief systems of our life are our mental capacity to follow a tradition. Whether constructive or destructive, human habits and mental capacities develops mostly beyond own awareness. As we see and listen, we invest in building our mental habits. Building psychological habits are an invisible phenomenon that shapes over time by the influence of our surrounding environment. Every sound we encounter, every image we observe, every situation we visualize that invest building our mental habits. The habit-building environment may be actual or virtual, but once a habit takes shape, it takes control of our life. Our brain values our habits as our identity, thus constantly engage in safeguarding our old habits, eventually we find ourselves resistance to new ideas at times. We feel an innate urge to follow our old habits through instinctive motivation and comply our habits through an inner force from within. Indeed, we humans act and behave very little by our knowledge and logic but a lot by our habits either

constructive or destructive. Predominantly we respond not by the beliefs and education but by what habits we possess.

Although childhood to adulthood is the best period, habits building technique functions at all times in our life. Every image we watch, every sound we hear, every smell we encounter, and every sense we visualize impacts our habit-building. Reading habits, watching TV shows, monitoring games and sports, browsing internet sites, using social media, and even learning something new can become our passion or mental habits. When we develop a mental habit of learning, reading, and rational thinking, the outcome is a higher level of knowledge and wisdom. When we build mental habits to know others' perspectives, practice empathy, mutual respect, sacrifice, justice, tolerance, and compassion, the outcome is peace and tranquility in the society. People of such societies enjoy self-actualization - the best outcome of constructive mental habits in pursuing wisdom.

Our sense of complying with social rules, norms, cultures, rituals, and even beliefs results from mental habits often build through the chameleon effect. We develop our mental habits as we see around us even sometimes we do not want to possess such habits. People often attain wisdom from wise associations, conversely, people who live in a destructive environment often suffer from behaviour modification. Humans possess an innate capacity to copy others and tend to imitate surrounding behaviors. Such spontaneous learning through imitating others is termed as chameleon effect. Researchers behind this study pointed out that coping behaviour builds likeness. It helps strengthen social bonding even when people are not aware of it.¹ Although copying and imitating seems indecent, the chameleon effect is a survival and progress tactic in human design. The chameleon effect is vital for human progress as a species since it carries forward the legacy of skills, experiences, knowledge, and learning.

Unity is the Result of Identical Mental Habits

Unity is the core survival need of evolutionary design in human; our brain constantly acts to enhance social unity and group bonding. Psychologist Andrew Whiten claims that humans are the most social creatures on earth, and thus it's our sociability, not our intelligence, that makes us unique (Whiten, 2000). Human brain seeks for power sources to collaborate; such unity often start from a nub. People who are decisive, credible and influential becomes the nub of the power and a snowball effect shapes a group identity. People also sense conscious or unconscious urgency to match trends of the surroundings. Thus people build unity through the essence of common interest, common practice and the social vibe. Albert Bandura pointed out this phenomenon

¹In 1999, New York University researchers Tanya Chartrand and John Bargh detailed three experiments that roughly mapped out how the chameleon effect works.

through *Social Learning Theory* and explained that our brain activities are highly resilient to the surrounding stimulations.² We tend to like what others like, and we feel disgusted when we observe surrounding people sense the same. Thus, we develop similar mental habits. As the social creature, humans are naturally motivated to form groups, and they form groups with people possessing similar physical and mental needs. Our needs in life direct and modify our responses, behaviours, and our physiology as well. We develop the habit of living in associations and feel happy to stay in a group. When we fail to live in associations, we suffer emotional breakdown; we often endure loneliness, depression, anxiety, and diverse psycho-somatic disorders.

Securing our identity within the social group encourage establishing self-worthiness among others. Our brain continuously evaluates and acts on what is needed to propagate own credibility among others. Due to such needs, people tend to display their superiority through every possible verbal and non-verbal signature opportunity. Over time, the urge to project own status, honour, respect, and dignity turns into mental habits. Our status competition, power politics, ranks, and promotions thus become the effect of our social need – a drive that originates from the need for self-existence. Physical and mental habits may sometimes stand opposite, and in such situations, we experience cognitive dissonance, conflicting minds, and dilemmas in our behaviour. In the daily life often we ignore our beliefs, knowledge, and education but follow the old habits. Our sense of justice, rationality, and logic are often the outcome of our mental habits.

Constructive Social Habits are Synonymous to Harmony

In our life journey, we experience social attachments, group identity, family attachments, emotional attachments with certain objects and brands, geographical attachments, and many more as our daily life features. These attachments often come from our habits, either physical or mental. Such attachment is imbedded in our habit architecture. Biologically humans thrive as social being but, when we try to lead a life against our biological design of collective living and develop isolated individualistic living habits, the result is often a disorder. When we ignore our essential elements of combined habits of mutual well-being and try to lead like a solitary being, we encounter numerous biological and psychological issues.

Seventy-five years' long study on adult life conducted by Harvard finds that people, who are emotionally better connected with their family members, friends, and community, enjoy better

² Albert Bandura was a Canadian-American psychologist who was the Professor of Psychology at Stanford University. His contributions to education and several fields of psychology, including social cognitive theory, therapy, and personality psychology, were well-known. He is known as the originator of social learning theory.

fulfilment in life and preserve better physical and mental health. Julianne Holt-Lunstad, PhD, a professor of psychology and neuroscience at Brigham Young University, reported, "Being connected to others socially is widely considered a fundamental human need—crucial to both wellbeing and survival." Researchers found that loneliness and social isolation are associated with a 40 percent increase in a person's risk of dementia.³ Therefore, constructive habits of cooperation, identical life values, and openness to diversity is a dire need in the society. The quality of our living, the social peace and stability essentially determines by the standard and practice of social habits.

We possess diverse habits in life. When some habits are socially or organizationally accepted, we often term them as the element of discipline. Our sense of obedience, self-order, norms, and values are our life habits. When we pursue certain collective habits, we observe discipline and harmony; when a society ignores the importance of constructive mental habits, they suffer from disharmony. Discipline is the key necessity of social harmony, which leads to peace, stability, and prosperity; conversely, disharmony brings destruction. The natural outcome of a harmonized social structure is enhanced cooperation and higher productivity. On the contrary, disharmony in life brings unhealthy competition, insecurity, and harmful power politics. Such societies often suffer from conflicts and violence. Disharmony comes from the diverse and unhealthy mental habits. At the meta-level, most social, national, and even global conflicts and crises are linked with different opinions, sense of interests, and varied perceptions - an output of dissimilar mental habits.

Destructive Mental Habits are the Root of Conflict and Disorder

Humans are driven by a combined effect of mutually inclusive needs of existence, reproduction, and habits. Often these needs complement each other, yet they also compete at times. Although humans survive and progress through the power of unity, they often also create disharmony. Displaying own status is a need to establish self-worth; however, power and status competition generate debate, inequality, and propagate unsound competition. People display diverse behavior for the same necessity of materializing higher existence. Same needs yet often opposite behaviour due to an inappropriate wisdom level in building mental habit. Thus we create differences instead of unity.

Most people follow someone whom they perceive successful in society. However, people recognize success by objective outcomes as humans motivate through tangible immediate needs. When a nation or an organization pursues and propagates the attainment of tangible objects as

³ *The Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, online 2018.

the meaning of success, the natural consequence is infrastructural development. It occurs due to material persuasiveness, through which people work hard with their utmost effort. Conversely, the same habit of pursuing materials encourages people to take a shortcut in gaining tangible benefits, and we find corruption, injustice, inequality, value deficit, conflict, and violence in the society.

Although humans architecture is collective survival, they often engage in conflicting and combating each other due to limited knowledge of self-worth and lack of higher wisdom. Disharmony and violence are directly opposite to the grand design of collectiveness in human species yet most people suffer from limited vision. People display disharmonious behavior due to inappropriate habit architecture in each mind.

When we spot someone as a gipsy, we distinguish them by their living habits. When we identify some people as Jews, Christians, or Muslims, we essentially recognize them by their belief habits. Often we get formatted in our mental habits in the form of conviction that shaped from childhood and thus we fail to think and rationalize many of our actions even being knowledgeable humans. While everybody knows, our life is an episode of a limited time consisting of a few years and months, most people engage their lifelong efforts to earn more money, status, and limitless power. The sense of such craving occurs due to our deep rooted mental habits. Diverse and destructive mental habits cause us to be apart from each other while constructive habits bring safety in societies. The definition of patriotism, dignity, honour, belongingness, values, principles, concept of the good life, success, and failure are the outcome of our mental patterns that have shaped social and national differences over time.

Indeed, humans are habit-driven creatures where mental habits are most vivid and often dominating. The command of mental habits is so powerful that people even accept supreme sacrifice to uphold their mental habits like beliefs, dignity, honour, and pride. The diversity of our national identities are the result of our mental habits that makes us possessing diverse nationalistic feelings. In pursuing our mental practices of own identity, we often label people as ‘we’ and ‘they,’ (Sapolsky 2022). Branding differences among people cause disparity; thus labelling people as ‘we and they’ become the core tipping point to arise conflict, escalate combat, and violence. In our daily life, we don’t fight with people whom we love. Rather, we accept a lot of sacrifice for people whom we consider as ‘we’ but fight whom we believe as ‘they.’ Such phenomenon is a psychological trap against unity yet observed almost everywhere. Indeed, an inappropriate, unhealthy, and diverse mental habits are the core issue for devastating outcomes of conflict and violence.

An Enduring Approach to Strategic Peace Building

People live in a society to achieve safety, security and progress through cooperation. Our brain always wants to act for more and more innovative connections with others to materialize our higher survival needs. In principle, the survival instincts that keep human always alive drives people to war and conflict between different groups (Von Clausewitz, 2008). However, humans always focus on a united human identity for the attainment of the highest survival needs. An individual human is too weak to survive, but collectively, humans are the best among all other species to conquer and construct. The concept of collective survival through cooperation and collaboration has made humans the most superior social beings on earth. So, we need to build the most constructive collective habits for our civilization to enhance highest level of cooperation and unity. We also need practical approach to reshape our destructive mental habits and eradicate disparity. We need mental habits to perceive all humans as single entity. We need to build our mental habits to love every human as own family members. We need to maximize the power of our spiritual and emotional strength to bring all humans under some universal viewpoints on building constructive mental habits. We also need to free ourselves from destructive mental habits like power and status competition. Nothing to excess in living, mutual respect, equality, justice, honesty, responsible behaviour, hard work, tolerance, and commitment to be the core universal human habits. An united effort to endure peace and prosperity is now a global necessity to re-capture the human title “The Best Species on Earth.”

Easy access to knowledge, comfortable learning environment, and global communication network have brought us in front of a new possibility where appropriate and constructive universal habits can be easier to build now. It shall foster more cooperation; enhance unity, peace, stability, and progress. Learning and practice of universal habits among nations can eradicate most of our social and intra or international mental differences and assist in building an even stronger united human identity on earth. It is possible to bring all humans of the globe under some common mental habits to build enduring peace.

Peace education has opened our conception that the whole world is the home of all humans and that present civilization has a single entity of humanity; as such, we need to master the art of living altogether. We must learn and progress with the highest degree of cooperation among us and wipe out the seeds of differences. We need to transform our mental habits so that it helps our combined survival and progress with the highest productivity as single human identity. We must shape and reshape our psychological habits to eradicate identity competition, power politics, status, and wealth-hunting contests. We need to establish and enjoy a mental habit of mutual respect, tolerance, gratitude, sacrifice, and practice essential human qualities. We need a calm and tranquil mindset that will help us all unite better than yesterday. We need to possess the habit of loving all humans and dedicate ourselves to the well-being of humanity irrespective of caste, colour, clan, status, or power. We need to eradicate our negative habits and transform them into constructiveness for more collaboration, support, and enhanced security in life. Today, it is a

global necessity promulgating and practicing the most suited universal human habits with superior human values to promote greater well-being for humanity.

Conclusion

Humans did not know farming or cultivation and thus suffered a lot of food crisis in ancient times. When our ancestors discovered the scientific techniques of cultivation, they could attain food guarantees for the year. Advanced technology has brought much more yield in a small land, and we grow a lot of food irrespective of seasons now. We, humans, have attained better food security even though we are a massive population in the world today. Similarly, if we engage ourselves to cultivate quality habits for universal unity, we shall find a violence-free world. We need a single virtue to build quality mental habits across the globe. We need to create a new world of peace and prosperity by eradicating our cognitive differences. Scholars of the world need to find out a global action plan to bring all humans in a common mental habit platform on the way to build enduring peace in the societies.

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